

Australian Research Data Commons

Vocabularies and research data

This guide explains what vocabularies are and how they are useful for supporting research. An overview of vocabulary services is included.

Who is this for?

This guide is intended for those needing a deeper understanding of the uses of research vocabularies.

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What is a vocabulary?

A vocabulary sets out the common language a discipline has agreed to use to refer to concepts of interest in that discipline. It is a model of the concepts in a discipline, with labels applied to the concepts and some kind of structure relating the concepts to each other.

Vocabularies take many forms. They include authority files, glossaries, dictionaries, gazetteers, code lists, taxonomies, subject headings, thesauri, semantic networks and ontologies. More technically (per <http://marinemetadata.org/guides/vocabs/vocdef>), a vocabulary is a set of terms or labels (words, codes, icons) that are used in a specific community to represent concepts.

How do vocabularies support research?

Data specification and description

When sharing data or combining data from different sources, there is a need for an agreed language to make sure the meaning of data is clear and explicit.

Researchers planning observation or surveys need to define their data items clearly. In formal system development environments this is done using metadata registries, data dictionaries, or data modelling software to define the permissible values/codes for data.

An agreed vocabulary (a standard) makes a good starting point for translating concepts into other vocabularies so that collaboration can occur.

Examples of vocabularies used to specify data values:

- Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Controlled Vocabularies (<https://ddialliance.org/controlled-vocabularies>)
- TOP Thesaurus of Plant Characteristics (<http://top-thesaurus.org/>)
- NEII Environmental Vocabularies (<http://www.neii.gov.au/vocabulary>)
- The Getty Vocabularies (<http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/>)
- ABS 2016 Census Data Dictionary (<https://www.abs.gov.au/ausstats/abs@.nsf/mf/2901.0>)

Data analysis

Ontology-mediated data integration

In this process scientists annotate data sets with semantically precise terms from an ontology, enabling reasoning across the data and transformations of the data for further analysis.

- Case study from genomics: Ontologies: Scientific Data Sharing Made Easy (<http://www.nature.com/scitable/topicpage/ontologies-scientific-data-sharing-made-easy-77972>)
- Case study from ecoinformatics: Ecoinformatics: supporting ecology as a data-intensive science (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2011.11.016>)

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis involves aggregating data and applying statistical analytical techniques. Data from different sources can be compared if they use a standard classification scheme (a kind of vocabulary). Without this it is difficult to combine or compare data from different sources and have a high degree of statistical confidence in the results.

Examples of statistical vocabularies:

- International Classification of Diseases (ICD) (<http://www.who.int/classifications/icd/en>), used for national mortality and morbidity statistics.
- Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC) (<https://www.abs.gov.au/ausstats/abs@.nsf/0/4AE-1B46AE2048A28CA25741800044242>) used for measuring and analysing research and experimental development (R&D) in Australia and New Zealand.

Data retrieval

Indexing vocabularies are used to tag items in library catalogues and search portals and to provide keywords for academic journal articles. Without indexing vocabularies search precision is reduced and valuable relevant research may not be retrieved. Indexing vocabularies are most effective when they mirror the searcher's terminology and conceptual perspective.

Examples of indexing vocabularies:

- Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) (<http://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>) used in the PubMed biomedical literature portal.
- Powerhouse Museum Object Name Thesaurus (<https://maas.museum/research/object-name-thesaurus>) used for indexing museum collections.
- Example of journal article with keywords: <http://dx.crossref.org/10.1111%2Fj.1365-2052.2005.01389>.

Vocabulary services

Traditionally most vocabularies were managed in custom software, and either printed or published as read-only web pages or downloadable documents (for example, see the APAIS Thesaurus - <https://www.vocabularyserver.com/apais/sobre.php>).

A vocabulary service is a machine-to-machine service that can support activities such as creating, managing and querying vocabularies.

Examples of vocabulary services:

- Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) (<http://lov.okfn.org/dataset/lov>)
- Library of Congress Authorities and Vocabularies service (<http://id.loc.gov/>)
- Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) (<https://ardc.edu.au/services/research-vocabularies-australia>)

SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System)

Knowledge organisation systems such as thesauri or any other type of structured controlled vocabulary can be represented using SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System). SKOS provides a standard way to represent knowledge organisation systems using the Resource Description Framework (RDF). This means that vocabulary information can be passed between computer applications in an interoperable way.

Find out more

Introduction to vocabularies:

- Marine Metadata Initiative (MMI) (<http://marinemetadata.org/guides/vocabs>) - a comprehensive explanation of vocabularies and their use

Standards:

- ANSI/NISO Z39.19 (<https://www.niso.org/publications/ansiniso-z3919-2005-r2010>) - Guidelines for the Construction, Format, and Management of Monolingual Controlled Vocabularies 2005 (revised 2010)
- ISO 25964 -1:2011 Information and documentation (<https://www.iso.org/standard/53657.html>) - Thesauri and interoperability with other vocabularies - Part 1: Thesauri for information retrieval
- SKOS (<http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos>) Simple Knowledge Organisation
- Resource Description Framework (RDF) (<http://www.w3.org/rdf>)

ARDC Controlled Vocabulary service:

- Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) (<https://ardc.edu.au/services/research-vocabularies-australia/>)

About the Australian Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) is a transformational, sector-wide initiative, working with sector, government, and industry partners to build a coherent national and collaborative research data commons. This will deliver a world-leading data advantage, facilitate innovation, foster collaboration and enhance research translation.

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